

THE HISTORY OF THE CONQUEST OF KHIVA KHANATE AND
KARAKALPAK TERRITORIES BY THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the plan of Russian subjugation of Central Asia and conquest of Khiva Khanate in the 70s of the XIX century.

There is a lot of information recorded by the participants of the trip about the excessive looting and brutal killing of the local population by the Russians during the conquest of Khiva Khanate.

Governor-General of Turkestan von Kaufmann stated about the war in his letter to Emperor Alexander II.

Keywords: Russia, Khiva Khanate, Emperor Alexander II, K.P. von-Kaufman, Nurota Mountains, Kyzylkum, Mangishloq, military

**ИСТОРИЯ ЗАВОЕВАНИЯ РОССИЙСКОЙ ИМПЕРИЕЙ ХИВИНСКОГО
ХАНСТВА И ТЕРРИТОРИЙ КАРАКАЛПАКИИ.**

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В данной статье представлен план покорения Россией Средней Азии и завоевания Хивинского ханства в 70-е годы XIX века.

Имеется много зафиксированных участниками поездки сведений о чрезмерных грабежах и жестоких убийствах местного населения русскими во время завоевания Хивинского ханства.

О войне генерал-губернатор Туркестана фон Кауфман заявил в своем письме императору Александру II.

Ключевые слова: Россия, Хивинское ханство, император Александр II, К.П. фон-Кауфмана, горы Нурота, Кызылкумы, Мангышлок, военные

By the 70s of the 19th century, Tsarist Russia had conquered most of Central Asia and was planning to conquer the Khanate of Khiva.

The governor-general of Turkestan, von Kaufmann, wrote to Emperor Alexander II on November 12, 1872, stating the inevitability of the war against Khiva. On November 23, 1872, a council was held in Petersburg under the chairmanship of the military minister D. Milyutin, where it was decided that next spring, the combined forces of the Caucasus, Orenburg and Turkestan military districts would launch an attack against Khiva. During the meeting with Alexander II in Petersburg on December 3, 1872, von Kaufan, who participated in the council, informed the emperor about the benefits of the planned military action. On December 12, 1872, the emperor approved the decision of the military council.

"However, the Russian state sent troops to Khorezm five years ago, and some of them died of thirst on the way to Khorezm, and some went to Khorezm to fight and die, and they still did not get any victory." Therefore, the emperor consulted with all the archon states in this chapter, and not knowing which way is best to go there, they made it necessary to send soldiers from four sides to Khorezm," wrote the historian Muhammad Yusuf Bayani.

In February-March 1873, Russian troops in Krasnovodsk, Mangishlok. Leaving Orenburg, Tashkent and Perovsk, Khiva khanate started marching in 5 directions.

22 companies, 1,800 Cossacks and 18 cannons under the command of the Governor General of Turkestan K.P. von Kaufman, 15 companies, 600 Cossacks, 8 cannons in the Orenburg detachment headed by Major General N.A. Verevkin, 12 companies in the Mangishlok detachment headed by Colonel Lomakin , there were 800 Cossacks, 8 cannons.

The total number of Russian soldiers was more than 13 thousand, they were armed with 56 cannons and rifles. During this period, the Khanate of Khiva had 2,000 cavalry, 4,000 infantry and 27 cannons, and they were mostly concentrated in the capital. 11,000 infantrymen formed the main part of the Russian army and left Tashkent on March 5, 1873. There were 6,000 horsemen and 2,500 artillerymen and 400 camels of baggage. When the army arrived in Jizzakh, it was 700 km from Sho'rkol through the Nurota Mountains and Kyzylkum. entered a more dangerous path. Near Bukantog, they were joined by Nikolay Konstantinovich, the brother of Tsar Alexander II, Duke Leitenbergsky, American journalist Mack Gahan, and others, who were in command of the 1400-strong army that left Qazali on March 6.

The troops from Orenburg under the command of General N.A. Verevkin, after resting for a while in the Emba fortress, on March 26 started moving towards the Ustyurt mountains with their baggage loaded on 5,000 camels. The Russians marched along the Aibugur gulf on the west coast of the Aral Sea, and on May 2, they reached the Yangikala fortress of the Khiva Khanate.

On April 9, the Caucasian detachment under the command of Colonel Lomakin, which set off from Kandirly Bay, passed through Besh-Aq Tog, Kyzil-Ayghir and joined the Orenburg detachment on May 12 in Kungyrot.

The 2,200-strong Russian troops of the Caucasus region under the command of Colonel Markozov, who set off from Chakishlar in the Atrek oasis towards Khiva, traveled 400 km without finding the wells on the caravan roads that passed through Karakum. they were forced to turn back on April 22 after setting off and 180 miles from their destination.

The advance detachments of the Russians continued to look for a convenient place to cross the river. While it was planned to move troops from the vicinity of Shorakhan and Tuynugli, the next one was considered desirable. With the help of a part of the ships, Russian soldiers were transferred to the left bank in 5 days. After a long and difficult journey, the Russians rested for a week in villages such as Yangibazar, Karvak, and Ovshar.

Russians coming through Ustyurt and from Mangishlok approached Kungyrot. Habniyazbi, Saidbi, Tajimuradbi, and Mansurbi, the bell dances, consulted about this and sent a message to the khan.

The Russians, after resting for a few days, fired several cannons at Kungirost and captured the city almost without a fight. The Biys, who fled the fortress, attacked the Russian detachments from time to time with about 300 horsemen on the way, but could not inflict significant losses.

When the Russians approached Khojaeli, by the order of Eltozar Inaq, Abdulla Mahram led a group of Turkmen horsemen from Imran and attacked in the grove. As a result, the Khiva people beheaded about ten Russian soldiers and returned with 13 horses and a quantity of weapons. 25 cavalry Cossacks sent to help the Russians arrived late and returned to the rear of Benatia.

After a short distance, the Russian troops encountered another group of Khiva troops. Armed with swords, shields, spears, and arrows, the Khiva people could not withstand the Russian rifles and cannons and retreated to Khojaeli. Here Inoqbek lined up his troops and was ready for battle. But according to the order of the khan brought by Khudoyar Koshbegi, the troops started to return to Khiva. At that time, Yavmud and Chavdar Turkmens began to attack the Russians who were in Maimana. They took horses and camels and went to Mangit. When they returned and went to battle again, they encountered a barrage of Russian bullets and could not stand it and retreated.

The Russians really saw the dangerous attacks of the Khiva patriots in the battles near the Mangit fortress. "A large number of Khiva horsemen appeared around us as if they had burst through the ground, they disappeared more and more, and quickly they began to attack us from all sides," wrote M. Alikhanov-Avasky in his memoirs. — Khan's troops brandished their swords in the air, shook the sky with shouts, and began to surround the Russian army... A group of horsemen suddenly rushed forward and burst into the ranks of our detachment. ... While their attack was being repulsed, a Turkmen cavalryman came out from behind us, from among the grass, attacked the captain who was standing in front of the squad's horse-cart and loaded camels, and shot him with his pistol. Then, after passing our carts and camels, he marched back in front of a whole platoon of infantry, waving his bare sword in the air, with a flamboyant display of his armor. Dozens of bullets fired from behind did not cause any damage" [3]," he wrote.

It was mentioned above that the Russians who came to the oasis did not harm the local people and that no hostility was felt even among the Khorezms. But the Russians were not always merciful. Bayani wrote about them, "They came to hunt a great game in Manqit Yavuk." - Verufkin ordered: the Russian soldiers attacked the village, massacred the inhabitants

regardless of age and gender, and then razed the village to the ground. After that, not being satisfied with this, the inhabitants of Manqit came to Manqit Castle, surrendered the castle to Russia and returned safely. and they would fly. Because they finished killing without leaving a living being, they grazed the city and left" [2]. Bayaniy writes that one thousand Russians, 4 generals and several officers and a number of soldiers were killed and 15 people were wounded in the battles near the Mangit fortress. Such cruelty continued later. General N.A. Verevkin, who came to Yangiyop, executed about 60 people gathered in the yard of Ganiboy, one of the local rich people.

A lot of information recorded by the participants of the trip has been preserved about the excessive looting and brutal killing of the local population by the Russians during the conquest of Khiva Khanate. Colonel M. Alikhanov-Avarsky testified about such nonsense: "I am in Mangit. The dead are lying among the property scattered in the streets and yards. I saw an Uzbek running down the street in a desperate situation. A Cossack is targeting him... the poor thing fell to the ground. By the way, such an incident also happened in Mangyt: a tall old man who was stumbling along a narrow street was cut in two places with a sword, blood was pouring out of his bare head and running down his face and beard. A drunken Cossack in a white fur coat with a blood-stained sword is chasing after him.

Walking around Manghit, I came across the stream that flows through the city. When I saw a few women in it who were drowning in water up to their necks, their faces changed from fear, my heart jumped and pulled me back. Not far from them, under the trees by the stream and in a narrow place between the walls, several elderly men and women were hiding. Perhaps they were also trembling and waiting for the moment of their death... As soon as they saw me, they all knelt down and began to cry, begging for safety".

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